

CALL: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01

TOPIC: HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-06

PROJECT: EOSC4CANCER, A European-wide foundation to accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research

PROJECT WEB SITE: www.eosc4cancer.eu

GRANT NUMBER: 101058427

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SCOPE OF THE POLICY BRIEF

This policy brief enables EU-funded projects contributing to the advancement of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) to report on progress and provide input for further policy analysis and development by the European Commission. This policy brief should be understood as complementary to the other mandatory reporting materials.

Policy background:

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a flagship EU initiative to deepen Open Science practices across the [European Research Area](#) (ERA). As such it contributes to several actions of the [ERA policy agenda](#) (in particular ERA action 1 & 8). EOSC is also recognised in the [European strategy for data](#) as the data space for science, research and innovation which shall be fully articulated with the other sectoral data spaces defined in the strategy.

Overall progress is steered by the EOSC tripartite governance involving the Union represented by the European Commission, the participating countries represented in the EOSC Steering Board and the research community represented by the EOSC Association. The second phase of development of EOSC (2021-2030) takes place in the context of the EOSC European co-programmed Partnership, which brings together the European Commission and the EOSC Association.

The [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA) co-developed with the entire EOSC community sets 3 General Objectives (GO), 14 Operational Objectives (OO) and 14 Action Areas (AA).

General Objectives (GO):

1. Open science becomes the ‘new normal’, by ensuring that open science practices and skills are rewarded and taught.
2. Researchers can seamlessly find, access, reuse and combine results, through the definition of common standards and the development of related tools and services.
3. A federated infrastructure under community governance enabling open sharing of scientific results is deployed and sustained.

Operational Objectives (OO):

1. Deliver and operate all the necessary components of the Minimum Viable EOSC to share openly research data, publications, software, tools and services while attracting increasing numbers and categories of users (public and private) (based on a governance structure representative of the various stakeholders and including domain-specific user environments supporting Open Science) by 2025;
2. Make monitoring systems to gather data and evidence on best Open Science practices accessible through EOSC (including the development of a dashboard to monitor the evolving landscape of policies, infrastructures and open resources made accessible via EOSC by 2023);
3. Increasingly mainstream Open Science skills in European research-performing organisations (RPOs) including through the uptake of curricula and training frameworks related to data stewardship through the lifespan of the Partnership;
4. Co-develop domain-specific standards and adopt Open Science practices through the engagement with research communities during the lifespan of the Partnership;
5. Provide the technical components of a FAIR ecosystem for uptake and customisation by the communities by 2023 (including open specifications, standards, schemas, application programming

interfaces (APIs), metadata frameworks supporting FAIR digital objects and their automated processing);

6. Provide the metrics and tools to measure the adoption of the FAIR principles for research artefacts and provide frameworks to help in certifying that repository services enable FAIR in EOSC throughout the lifespan of the Partnership;
7. Co-develop a first generation of a robust pan-European network of infrastructures for software source code (including incentives for the effective documentation and sharing of research software) by 2025;
8. Co-design and adopt a Rewards and Recognition framework for FAIR and open data practices in research during the lifespan of the Partnership.
9. Implement and evolve the EOSC Rules of Participation and onboarding process for EOSC providers and increase the number of service providers and services offered progressively over the course of the Partnership.
10. Deploy and operate an authentication and authorisation infrastructure (AAI) framework to manage user identity and access by 2024;
11. Implement the EOSC persistent identifier (PID) policy and architecture by 2025;
12. Co-develop a minimum metadata framework and provide a common search and access mechanism to EOSC resources across the EOSC federation by 2025;
13. Continuously monitor and promote the increased uptake of core services and EOSC resources, access to EOSC Exchange tools and services and ensure a feedback loop with the users;
14. Define models for availability and costing of services across borders by 2023.

<u>Action Areas (AA) of a technical nature:</u>	<u>Action Areas (AA) related to boundary conditions:</u>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifiers 2. Metadata and ontologies 3. FAIR metrics and certification 4. Authentication / authorisation infrastructure 5. User environments 6. Resource provider environments 7. EOSC Interoperability Framework 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. Rules of Participation 9. Landscape monitoring 10. Business models 11. Skills and training 12. Rewards and recognition 13. Communication 14. Widening to public and private sectors and going global

More information can be found from:

- https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science/european-open-science-cloud-eosc_en
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/open-science-cloud>
- <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about>

FEEDBACK ON PROGRESS AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS (MAX 6P)

A. Overview of contributions in relation to the EOSC policy and EOSC SRIA objectives.

AA User Environment and AA Resource Provider Environments

EOSC4Cancer is working on the development and enhancement of virtual research environments, including analysis-based and visualization systems. The analysis of research data will be facilitated by two environments: Galaxy and OpenVRE, which are fully functional and already used by Life Sciences researchers across different projects and communities. In the context of cancer research, both of them will have accessible and interoperable research software and analytical workflows and will contribute to the standardization and harmonization of data, its connection to specific tools and pipelines, and the reproducibility of results. The deliverable documenting the work and deployment of these virtual research environments will be available by the end of the project (February 2025).

In addition, EOSC4Cancer provides a specific cancer data analysis environment based on the open-source platform cBioPortal, allowing to make the specific longitudinal data analyses typically needed for cancer research, following the events along the patient journey (starting at first diagnosis and first-line treatment, following the entire disease progression towards the treatments during the advanced stages of the disease). cBioPortal integrates and visualizes cancer genomics data and other high-dimensional data types together with

clinical data and disease outcomes. It has been included in most of the EOSC4Cancer use cases as well as hundreds of research projects across the globe. Within EOSC4Cancer specific integrations with well-established resources such as the EGA (the European Genome-phenome Archive deemed as the repository for access controlled -omics data) and XNAT (radiology data archive) will be developed and implemented. Interestingly, cBioPortal is considered a transversal platform for the different EOSC4Cancer use cases. The use cases all take as reference colorectal cancer, considering its high incidence across the general population and the availability of different data types along the cancer patient journey (prevention, diagnosis, and treatment).

Indeed, the activity of the project is centered on the use and re-use of FAIR cancer-related data from distributed repositories, research projects, as well as primary cancer care centers. Interoperability between different data types is strongly based on FAIR data standards. Thus, EOSC4Cancer will contribute with protocols and operating procedures to facilitate the progressive adoption of the FAIR principles across data sources but also for research software, including workflows. Moreover, the use of sensitive data should not represent major challenges but imply new requirements, i.e. the sensitive nature of cancer-related data shouldn't prevent taking the necessary steps to make data FAIR under the principles of as open as possible, as closed as necessary. Additionally, special attention is given to other digital objects that enable research, e.g. research software, both in terms of FAIR and quality. Such efforts should contribute to enhancing research software, including analytical workflows, as a fundamental element of any research activity and, thus, relevant to guarantee research reproducibility and reusability.

Beyond these three systems and the duration of the project, EOSC4Cancer is working on a roadmap to outline the future federated digital infrastructure supporting Cancer Research in Europe. This roadmap will include sustainability plans and costing models, responsibilities, and access mechanisms after EOSC4Cancer ends. On top of that, it will take into account the input from patient organizations as well as the roadmaps related to European Cancer landscape including the EU Mission on Cancer, EOSC projects (especially EOSC-Life, EuroScienceGateway, BY-COVID, SciLake, Skills4EOSC), other EU projects (ranging from CSA ones like 4.unCAN.eu and HealthyCloud, data-generating ones like canSERV, infrastructure-related ones like GDI and EUCAIM, and the one from the European Health Data Space, HealthData@EU) and other initiatives with a component of data management and analysis. The roadmap will be validated in consultation with various key stakeholders within and outside of EOSC4Cancer, including communities in EU Cancer Mission, cancer research, data initiatives, cancer patients/survivors and EOSC. It is important to highlight that the roadmap is done in conjunction with different EU Research infrastructures such as ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN and EuroBioImaging, as it is expected that they would strongly contribute to the long-term sustainability and alignment with the various on-going projects and others to come.

Two consultation events will be held with the stakeholder forum and other invited stakeholders, the first one being on 17 -18 October 2023. The resulting roadmap will be delivered in February 2025.

AA Metadata and ontologies

An important step towards interoperability in cancer research lies in enabling the connection of different elements and research data, which requires accurate metadata descriptions and use of common ontologies for the content in order to facilitate the reuse of data. EOSC4Cancer will provide recommendations, guidelines, and best practices in the form of reports and Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) to properly capture and describe data through the use of appropriate data models, dictionaries, and ontologies.

This work will focus on the use of common data models, the selection of widely-extended controlled vocabularies and ontologies, as well as the needs of modeling data/metadata before capturing it. Recommendations will be transversal to the field although particular examples will be given using metastatic colorectal cancer datasets.

We also bring together existing best practices in this domain that are currently being developed and applied in practice such as AACR GENIE in the US, the minimal dataset for cancer from the 1+MG/B1MG project, and other data collections from comprehensive cancer centers. Interactions with projects like the HealthData@EU through its pilot projects should also contribute towards understanding how to interoperate with data captured initially for treating patients and then repurpose for research. This particular effort is done in the context of the European Health Data Space (EHDS). These best practices are highlighted and presented among the EOSC4Cancer community to raise awareness of existing data models and promote their adoption.

The report will be ready by the end of the project, while recommendations and best practices are collected during the project and shared openly to the community as soon as they are ready.

AA Skills and training

EOSC4Cancer is working on the development of a training portfolio related to cancer research. It will provide resources, skills, and training to biomedical researchers, healthcare professionals, and others in the field so they are exposed to the use of diverse data types together with different tools and elements developed by EOSC4Cancer.

A dedicated "Cancer Data view" in the ELIXIR Research Data management Kit (RDMkit; <https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>) that captures good practices, training resources and connects to data experts across Europe will be established.

EOSC4Cancer will act as a key demonstrator in Skills4EOSC as a domain specific pilot. It will be delivered by the end of 2024.

B. Key contributions subject to wider dissemination by the European Commission.

Use cases are pivotal to the EOSC4Cancer project guiding the more technical work packages with practical input on the needs of oncology research projects. The use cases are offered by five real-life research projects in the area of colorectal cancer following the patient journey from disease onset (prevention) to early diagnosis and treatment to late-stage treatment. The use cases are exemplars for data standardisation needs, minimal common data models, research software, and data repositories that can be realised across research projects and, ideally, transfer to other tumor types.

C. Synergies with other stakeholders.

The EOSC-Life project, which creates a foundation data space with the 13 Life Sciences Research Infrastructures in EOSC, is used as a reference within the EOSC4Cancer project: technical work packages follow its guidelines and practices to facilitate access to cancer data and facilities. EOSC4Cancer will build on data catalogues, workflow and research software systems, ensuring software good practices and provenance, e.g., using RO-CRATE, under FAIR guidance. EOSC4Cancer will also rely on the work done in EOSC-Life in terms of users' Authentication and Authorization as well as on the computational capabilities envisioned by EOSC-Life WP7, which also deals with costs modeling. The project will leverage previous developments on analyzing sensitive data under access control and serve as reference use-case to the EuroScienceGateway project in the form of a sensitive data use case.

Interestingly, there is a strong conceptual alignment with the BY-COVID project as both projects aim to enhance researchers' capabilities to perform their scientific activities through exemplar use-cases in infectious diseases (BY-COVID) and cancer research (EOSC4Cancer), respectively. To be able to answer use-cases requirements, both projects count with dedicated efforts on analysis and interpretation platforms, data interoperability activities and data sources description, discovery and mobilization.

Lastly, EOSC4Cancer is also collaborating with SciLake, which has cancer as one of its use cases. Specifically, the aim of SciLake is automating the generation of domain-specific knowledge graphs by leveraging data infrastructures. The cancer pilot case, which is led by members of the EOSC4Cancer consortium, will use the services developed by the SciLake project. Specifically, the pilot will be interlinked with aggregated output that is continuously produced through analysis of omics data as these are generated by national efforts and cancer research projects, following the standards and protocols that EOSC4Cancer is defining.

HealthyCloud is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project aiming to generate a strategic agenda for the future Health Research and Innovation Cloud (HRIC) for the secondary use of health data across Europe. Recommendations, best practices and other outputs generated in the context of HealthyCloud are nowadays taken by EOSC4Cancer, which will contribute towards the project's long-term sustainability and its adoption by the coming projects in the context of EOSC and the EHDS. At the same time, such contributions will contribute to bringing EOSC and EHDS together for the development of the HRIC.

The stakeholder classification, reported as part of the Digital Skills for FAIR and Open Science by the EOSC Executive Board, was used for the stakeholder engagement, communication and engagement methodology in EOSC4Cancer. It is also used as part of the EOSC4Cancer work package (WP5) to stratify the skills and training needs for the EOSC stakeholders in EOSC4Cancer.

EOSC4Cancer contributes actively to the Horizon Europe Communication and Engagement Group and in the EOSC Forum through WP6. The stakeholder forum created by EOSC4Cancer includes diverse stakeholders, including from research, healthcare, industry, EOSC Association and EOSC projects and will play an important role in the development of the roadmap of the federated digital infrastructure for Cancer Research.

The ELSI framework of EOSC4Cancer will be aligned with the work of the Joint Action Programme Towards European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) on different governance models for the exchange and secondary use of health-related data.

Finally, there is a strong alignment with 4.unCAN.eu, a CSA project of the EU Cancer Mission, for designing a federated data hub for cancer research data leveraging existing efforts, projects, initiatives, and research infrastructures. Such a data hub should ideally be connected with the European Health Data Space (EHDS) to ensure the optimal use of health-related data for research purposes. The on-going HealthData@EU pilot project on cancer genomics illustrates clearly those benefits. The CanSERV project, which will provide different data types produced in diverse scenarios, will complement the possibilities of data generation efforts by illustrating the benefits of generating research data for advancing cancer research. Altogether, these alignment efforts will translate into recommendations for the European Cancer Mission and will build a reasonable basis of protocols and technical developments for future projects.

D. EOSC challenges and lessons learnt of a policy nature.

EOSC4Cancer tackles a very specific topic: health-related research, specifically in the context of cancer. Similarities with other projects exist with BY-COVID as the main example, although it focuses on a different type of diseases (infectious as opposed to non-infectious). The SciLake project has a use case related to cancer, although it is not health specific. So, none of them are approaching cancer research as only and main focus. Also, it is the only EOSC project relating explicitly to the EU Mission on Cancer. Thus, the challenge that we might have is that the people within the EOSC Landscape do not have specific knowledge about cancer research. Thus, we are crafting our messages for EOSC related activities in a way that focusses more on technology and less on elements that are very specific to cancer research.

A specific challenge faced by EOSC4Cancer is the sensitivity nature of the data: health data -specially the genomics one- is considered highly privacy-sensitive, and therefore classified as special category data according to the GDPR regulation. This requires a significant additional effort in terms of technical precautions and legal agreements, which often extend beyond what is legally required in order to reassure data providers. Thus, EOSC4Cancer is working closely with other relevant projects facing similar challenges like BY-COVID, EUCAIM and GDI to have a similar approach for the management of sensitive data under access control in a federated manner.

To address this challenge, the EOSC Association could ensure that the dissemination levels (i.e., domain specific, general audience, etc.) and in accordance with the delivered messages to the EOSC community. It could also provide sessions that are domain specific, so the level of understanding of the audience would be greater and the presentations could be more focused on the real challenges, rather than having to adhere to a general and high-level overview.

E. Link to other EU policy priorities (beyond EOSC).

The objective of EOSC4Cancer is to provide protocols, best practices, reference implementations and access to research software, including analytical workflows, for accelerating and standardising cancer-related research in the context of the European Cancer Mission. To make that possible, EOSC4Cancer is based on different use-cases that serve as examples of the Cancer Patient Journey. Thus, It will contribute to developing plans for the Cancer Data Space with the ultimate goal of informing the EU Cancer Mission. EOSC4Cancer is closely collaborating with UNCAN.eu to achieve the integration of existing research infrastructures, e.g. ELIXIR, BBMRI, EATRIS, ECRIN, EuroBioImaging; relevant initiatives and projects like 1+MG, B1MG, GDI, EUCAIM, CanSERV, and cancer data infrastructures. It will ensure that the cancer use-case is covered by the maturity models currently being developed by B1MG, ELIXIR-CONVERGE, GA4GH, and other projects. Bringing together those efforts would facilitate incorporating different perspectives, scenarios and aspects for organisations seeking to share responsibly sensitive human data for research purposes. The results of the EOSC4Cancer use-case implementations will cover the Cancer Patient Journey, from prevention and

early diagnosis to treatments in advanced stages of the disease. These outputs, in form of guidelines and recommendations, will serve as guides for the development of the EU Cancer Mission portfolio.

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) is a policy-framing and technical standard-setting organisation that aims to enable responsible genomic data sharing within a human rights framework. Their standards and guidelines will be adopted throughout the project and will be incorporated in the technical developments of the EOSC4Cancer Consortium, which will be assured by the contribution of project participants to the GA4GH.

The European Health Data Space pilot project has a use case to demonstrate the use of genomic data together with health data in the context of cancer. This use case is the link between HealthData@EU and GDI; and GDI will leverage what EOSC4Cancer is doing in the EOSC environment. Through the consortium partners leading the cancer use case in the Pilot project, EOSC4Cancer will continue to provide input into the development of the EHDS.

Overall, EOSC4Cancer is working to serve cancer researchers, and ultimately cancer patients, by facilitating data access from cancer networks and European research infrastructures, using open data standards (taking GA4GH and ICGC as references in the field of cancer), building on and further collaborating with the EOSC ecosystem, synergizing with stakeholders like 1+MG/B1MG and EUCAIM, and contributing towards the European Health Data Space and the European Cancer Mission.

SUSTAINABILITY AND LEGACY (MAX 1P)

This section should be filled only by projects in their final reporting period.

N/A